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Научная статья

ДЕТЕРМИНАНТЫ МИРОВОГО РЫНКА ЧАСОВ

THE GLOBAL WATCH MARKET DETERMINANTS

КУЗЬМЕНКО СВЕТЛАНА СЕРГЕЕВНА,

доцент кафедры международной экономики,

*ФГБОУ ВО «Донецкий национальный университет экономики и торговли имени
Михаила Туган-Барановского».*

KUZMENKO SVETLANA SERGEEVNA,

Associate Professor of International Economics Department,

*FSBEI HE “Donetsk National University of Economics and Trade named after
Mikhail Tugan-Baranovsky”.*

В статье систематизированы конъюнктурные тенденции развития мирового рынка часов в современных условиях. Определены специфические аспекты внешнеэкономической деятельности предприятий на рынке часов. Методология исследования подразумевает всестороннее изучение детерминантов и определяющих факторов, влияющих на внешнеэкономическую активность ТНК часовой отрасли с учетом рыночной конъюнктуры; структурный и динамический обзор статистических сведений о международной торговле, а также обобщение полученных данных. Конъюнктурные тенденции развития мирового рынка часов в современных условиях определяют специфические аспекты внешнеэкономической деятельности основных хозяйствующих субъектов исследуемой отрасли, а также параметры диагностики в средне- и долгосрочной перспективе. Подтверждается детерминация мирового рынка часов экономической доминантой.

The article systematizes the current trends in the development of the global watch market in modern conditions. It identifies the specific aspects of foreign trade activities of enterprises in the watch market. The research methodology involves a comprehensive study of the determinants and factors influencing the foreign economic activity of TNCs in the watch industry, taking into account market conditions; a structural and dynamic review of statistical data on international trade, as well as a summary of the obtained results. The current trends in the development of the global watch market determine the specific aspects of the foreign trade activities of the main economic entities in the industry, as well as the diagnostic parameters in the medium and long term. The determination of the global watch market by economic factors is confirmed.

Ключевые слова: *мировой рынок, рынок часов, международная торговля, качество, спрос, экспорт, смарт часы.*

Key words: *global market, watch market, international trade, quality, demand, export, smart watches.*

In the contemporary environment, analyzing the foreign economic activities of companies operating in the global watch market has become particularly important and relevant. The significance of this topic is driven by several factors, including the significant share of watch products in international trade and the active participation of the Russian Federation in the global trade and economic system. The global watch market encompasses a wide range of products that primarily serve the purpose of measuring time or performing time-related operations. This category includes

both wearable watches (wristwatches, pocketwatches, and stopwatches) and other types of watches (tablewatches, wallwatches, alarm clocks, marine chronometers, and car clocks), as well as time recording devices, time interval meters, and timers. Products in this category can be made of various materials, including precious metals, and can be decorated with pearls (natural or cultured), as well as precious and semi-precious stones (natural, synthetic, or restored).

The specifics of companies' foreign trade operations organization in the global watch market were analyzed by the following researchers: Ankudinova Yu.A. [1, p. 62–64], Poltoratsky M.S. [10, p. 51], Drobnitsa I.K. [2, p. 70–82], Tindova M.G. [13, p. 60–64], Yashin V.N. [14, p. 86–89], Indinok D.A. [3, p. 96–114] and others. The economic literature does not provide a comprehensive analysis of the determinants and key factors of the global watch market, which highlights the need for further research in this area.

The aim of this work is to study the determinants of the global watch market. To achieve this aim, the following tasks must be completed: to systematize the current trends in the development of the global watch market; to identify the specific aspects of foreign trade activities in the watch market.

The main categories of the global watch market [2, p. 81; 12; 13, p. 60; 14, p. 86] are presented in Table 1. The terminology of the studied market includes the main qualitative characteristics of watches (water resistance, isochronous oscillations), functions and components (world time, time equation, chronograph, chronometer, tachymeter, tourbillon, alarm clock, guilloche), and types of products (premium, luxury, and entry-level branded watches), which together form a set of parameters for assessing the specifics of industry production.

The main categories of watch quality assessment in the global market [12] are presented in Table 2, which contains positions on qualimetry methods and “quality marks”.

Conjunctural trends in the development of the global watch market [13, p. 61–64; 14, p. 85] are presented in table 3. The trends under consideration are related to changes in consumer preferences, technological advancements, and the influence of legislation and economic factors. Some of these trends include: increased demand for smartwatches with fitness tracking, heart rate monitoring, notifications, and connectivity features; personalization of watches, where consumers create unique models that reflect their individual style; sustainability, where brands use eco-friendly materials (recycled metals, eco-friendly packaging) and adhere to ethical production practices; and the growth of online retail, where watch brands increasingly bypass traditional retail channels and sell directly to consumers through their websites and online marketplaces.

Table 1. The main categories of the global watch market

Categories	Definitions and interpretations of definitions
Premium brand watches	Business entities that install their own mechanisms inside their watches, which are invented, designed, and assembled within the factory walls; the appearance of such watches is created by professional jewelers; this group is based on Swiss companies that have been on the market for hundreds of years and produce limited-edition products.
Luxury brand watches	Prestigious brands of major watch companies with a rich history and numerous admirers around the world; among the models, there are both classic and sporty examples, as well as avant-garde and innovative experiments; in terms of functionality and exclusivity of materials, they are on par with the highest level, but they use ready-made technologies.
Entry-level brands	Using reliable Swiss movements, high-quality materials, sapphire crystal, international guarantees, and a noble exterior, the companies create affordable accessories for everyday use.
Guilloche	A delicate engraved pattern on the dial.

Isochrony of oscillations	A physical term that means that the oscillation period of a balance is independent of its amplitude.
Water resistance	An important quality of a watch case is its protection against moisture.
Alarm	A sound function that plays a signal at a predetermined time.
Tourbillon	In French, “whirlwind”; a device patented in 1801 by Abraham-Louis Breguet, designed to compensate for gravitational effects on the watch mechanism.
Tachymeter	A scale on the chronograph bezel that allows you to calculate the speed of the watch wearer.
Chronometer	Especially accurate watches whose characteristics are confirmed by the corresponding certificate of the Swiss Institute for Testing of Chronometers (Controle Officiel Suisse des Chronometres, abbreviated as COSC).
Chronograph	A sports function that allows you to measure time intervals with the accuracy of the balance frequency.
Equation of time	An exotic function that shows the difference between the average (standard) and true solar time; this difference is not constant.
World Time (Worldtimer)	A function that allows you to see the current time in different (usually 24) time zones on Earth.

Compiled by the author based on [2, p. 81; 12; 13, p. 60; 14, p. 86]

In the contemporary world, a watch is one of those accessories that can be used to determine a person's social status, as well as their taste, habits, life goals, and values. The global market offers a wide range of brands that can be categorized into three main categories: premium, luxury, and entry-level brands.

Table 2. Main categories of watch quality assessment in the global market [12]

Categories	Definitions and interpretations of definitions
Qualimetric quality assessment	A set of methods for measuring and quantifying the quality of watches, which are used to make informed decisions in the process of managing their quality.
Methods of qualimetry	Measurement, registration, calculation, organoleptic, expert, and sociological methods.
Fleurieu Quality	The watch “quality mark” established in 2001 by manufacturers from the Fleurier region; it is considered the most complex of all existing marks, as it includes a series of Chronofiable tests that simulate the long-term wear and tear of a watch.
The Geneva Brand	The Geneva canton coat of arms, which has been stamped on watches produced in accordance with regional quality requirements since 1886.
Geneva Stripes	A decorative pattern of vertical or horizontal stripes that is used to cover platinum and bridges.

The first group includes business entities that install their own mechanisms inside their watches, which are invented, designed, and assembled within the factory walls. The appearance of these watches is created by professional jewelers. This group is dominated by Swiss companies that have been in the market for hundreds of years and produce limited editions of their products.

The second group includes prestigious brands of major watch companies that have a rich history and numerous fans around the world. These models include both classic and sporty designs, as well as avant-garde and innovative experiments. They offer the same level of functionality and exclusivity as high-end watches, but use ready-made technologies.

Entry-level watch manufacturers use reliable Swiss movements, high-quality materials, sapphire glass, international guarantees, and a noble exterior to create affordable accessories for everyday use.

Thus, modern enterprises use the same materials and technologies to create products across a significant price range [13, p. 60].

Among the leading watch manufacturers in the world, the following companies can be classified (table 4): Swatch Group (Switzerland), which produces watches under the following brands: Breguet, Omega, Rado, Tissot, and Calvin Klein; Seiko Group (Japan), which produces watches under the following brands: Seiko, Grand Seiko, Pulsar, and Orient; Fossil Group (USA), which produces watches under the following brands: Fossil, Relic, Michele, Zodiac, and Skagen; and so on [4–9; 14, p. 85–86].

Table 3. Conjunctural trends in the global watch market in the current conditions

№	Conjunctural trends
1.	High level of competition in the global watch market
2.	A trend aimed at improving the quality of watches and watch mechanisms
3.	Switzerland's leadership among countries exporting products whose watchmaking is recognized as the highest quality in the world
4.	Increase in Swiss watch exports to Asian countries
5.	A significant decrease in Switzerland's exports to the Americas
6.	The influence of fashion trends, brand reputation, and product price on consumer choice of watches
7.	Brand positioning, the use of famous personalities in product promotion, product placement, participation in and support for various events, such as exhibitions, shows, sports competitions, publications in specialized media, and a special approach to the design and location of stores
8.	High growth rates in the global watch manufacturing industry
9.	The following factors have the most significant impact on the cost of a watch: case material, limited edition, tourbillon function, bracelet material, distinctive features, and skeleton function
10.	For French business entities, the main pricing factors are the case material, the limited edition of the collection, and the use of precious stones in the design
11.	For Italian business entities, the main pricing factors are the use of precious stones and the material of the case
12.	For American watch companies, the cost of a watch is determined by the brand. The influence of other factors, such as the material of the case and bracelet, the presence of various functions or precious stones in the design, is not significant
13.	The main pricing factors for Swiss watch companies are the presence of a tourbillon function, the material of the case, and the skeleton function
14.	Mechanical watch movements are mostly found in men's watches, while quartz movements are more common in women's watches
15.	Increased water resistance and additional features such as a calendar, moon phase, tourbillon, skeleton, and tachymeter are typical for men's watches
16.	Women's models are largely characterized by the presence of precious stones in the design, different color schemes, and the dependence of the bracelet material on the material of the case and the color of the dial

Compiled by the author based on [13, p. 61–64; 14, p. 85].

The above-mentioned economic entities produce the following types of wristwatches (based on their principle of operation): mechanical, quartz, and electronic. Smartwatches (also known as

smart clocks) are highly popular among consumers, and their leading manufacturers include Garmin Ltd. (USA), Samsung Group (South Korea), and Apple Inc. (USA) [14, p. 86].

Table 4. Main brands of the world's leading watch manufacturers

№	Company	Brands	Country
Traditional wristwatches			
1.	Swatch Group	Breguet, Omega, Rado, Tissot, Calvin Klein	Switzerland
2.	Seiko Group	Seiko, Grand Seiko, Pulsar, Orient	Japan
3.	Fossil Group	Fossil, Relic, Michele, Zodiac, Skagen	USA
Smart watches (smart clocks)			
1.	Garmin Ltd.	Garmin	USA
2.	Samsung Group	Samsung	South Korea
3.	Apple Inc.	Apple	USA

Compiled by the author based on [4–9; 14, p. 85–86].

The specifics of enterprises' foreign trade activities in the global watch market are manifested in the aspects [11] presented in table 5.

Table 5. Specific aspects of enterprises' foreign trade activities in the global watch market [11]

№	Specific aspects
1.	Foreign trade activities in accordance with the global ranking of the best-selling watches: Casio Collection Vintage Iconic F-91W-1Q, Orient Automatic, DKNY Soho Bracelet Watch, Timberland Henniker II, Fossil Sport Cuff Chronograph Leather Watch – Black, Calvin Klein Minimal, Swiss Military Hanowa Patriot Chrono, Diesel Mega Chief
2.	Adaptation of foreign trade activities in accordance with the global ranking of the best-selling women's watches: Jaeger-LeCoultre (Switzerland), Cartier (Switzerland), Glashütte Original (Germany), Moritz Grossmann (Germany), Grand Seiko (Japan), Dolce & Gabbana (Italy)
3.	Prioritization of foreign trade activities based on the global ranking of the most popular men's watches: Casio, Tissot, Guess, Diesel, Orient, Citizen, Swatch, Fossil
4.	Actualization of foreign trade activities according to the ranking of the most popular Swiss watches: Vacheron Constantin, Omega, Patek Philippe, Rolex
5.	The desire to preserve the true values and traditions of watchmaking, as well as the high level of professionalism and skill of watchmakers, is at the forefront of initiatives by Swiss organizations and institutions, including the Foundation for High Watchmaking Art.
6.	The need for coordinated foreign trade activities by all watch companies and related economic and other structures, as well as the creation of a set of instructions that ensure the long-term survival and successful development of the watch industry
7.	Educational work among the population of developing countries through their acquaintance with the values of high watchmaking through specific examples, contributing to increased readiness to perceive these values and increased efficiency of foreign trade activities of enterprises in the studied market

The determinants of the global watch market in the context of geopolitical turbulence are manifested in accordance with the specifics of the global watch industry and the characteristics of consumer demand:

- 1) Growing demand for luxury watches — consumers value craftsmanship, exclusivity, and status.

2) Demand for multifunctional watches for an active lifestyle — brands are diversifying their offerings to include models focused on sports and adventure.

3) Interest in limited editions — collectors and enthusiasts are increasingly seeking out exclusive and custom-made watches that offer unique designs and personalized features.

The determinants of the global watch market in the context of geopolitical turbulence manifest themselves according to technological aspects:

1) The introduction of advanced features in smartwatches, such as improved chipsets, energy-efficient high-resolution displays, and connectivity options beyond Bluetooth and Wi-Fi.

2) The use of AI and machine learning, which makes smartwatches more intelligent by providing personalized alerts and recommendations based on user behavior and preferences.

3) Hybrid watch design — combines traditional analog dials with smartwatch features, appealing to consumers seeking a balance between classic elegance and modern functionality.

The global watch market is determined by economic dominance:

1) Growing disposable incomes in emerging markets, such as the Asia-Pacific region, which drives demand for mid-range and high-end watches.

2) The impact of urbanization and the growing culture of an active lifestyle in developing economies, where consumers seek affordable yet high-tech wearables to support their wellness goals.

3) Economic constraints, such as the high cost of luxury watches, which are only accessible to a narrow segment of affluent consumers.

Thus, based on the results of the study, the goal has been achieved and the objectives have been met. Summarizing the research findings on the determinants of the global watch market, it is advisable to draw the following conclusions:

1. The current trends in the development of the global watch market include: a high level of competition in the global watch market; a trend towards improving the quality of watches and watch mechanisms; Switzerland's leadership among countries exporting watches, which are recognized as the highest quality in the world; an increase in Switzerland's exports of watches to Asian countries; and a significant decrease in Switzerland's exports to countries in the Americas; the influence of fashion trends, the manufacturer's reputation, and the product's price on consumer choice of watches; brand positioning, the use of famous personalities in product promotion, product placement, participation in and support for various events such as exhibitions, fashion shows, sports competitions, and publications in specialized media; a unique approach to the design and location of stores; and the rapid development of the global watch manufacturing industry. The factors that most significantly impact the cost of a watch include the material of the case, the limited edition of the watch, the presence of a tourbillon function, the material of the bracelet, the presence of distinctive features, and the presence of a skeleton function; for French business entities, the main pricing factors for watches are the case material, the limited edition of the collection, and the use of precious stones in the design; for Italian business entities, the main pricing factors are the use of precious stones and the case material; for American companies, the cost of a watch is determined by the brand; for Swiss watch companies, the main pricing factors are the presence of a tourbillon function, the case material, and the skeleton function; mechanical watch movements are predominantly found in models designed for men, while quartz movements are more commonly used in women's watches; increased water resistance and the presence of additional features such as a calendar, moon phase, tourbillon, skeleton, and tachymeter are typical for men's watches; women's models are largely characterized by the presence of precious stones in their design, various color schemes, and the dependence of the bracelet material on the case material and dial color.

2. The specifics of foreign trade activities of enterprises in the global watch market are manifested in the following aspects: the implementation of foreign trade activities in accordance with the world ranking of the best-selling watches: Casio Collection Vintage Iconic F-91W-1Q, Orient

Automatic, DKNY Soho Bracelet Watch, Timberland Henniker II, Fossil Sport Cuff Chronograph Leather Watch — Black, Calvin Klein Minimal, Swiss Military Hanowa Patriot Chrono, Diesel Mega Chief; adaptation of foreign trade activities in accordance with the world ranking of the best-selling women's watches: Jaeger-LeCoultre, Cartier, Glashütte Original, Moritz Grossmann, Grand Seiko, Dolce & Gabbana; prioritization of foreign trade activities in accordance with the world ranking of the most popular men's watches: Casio, Tissot, Guess, Diesel, Orient, Citizen, Swatch, Fossil; actualization of foreign trade activities in accordance with the rating of Swiss watches sold: Vacheron Constantin, Omega, Patek Philippe, Rolex; the desire to preserve the true values and traditions of watchmaking, the high level of professionalism and skill of watchmakers at the head of initiatives of Swiss organizations and institutions; the need for coordinated foreign trade activities of all watch companies and related business and other structures, as well as the creation of a set of instructions that ensure the survival and successful development of the watch industry in the long term; educational work among the population of developing countries through their acquaintance with the values of fine watchmaking using concrete examples, contributing to increased readiness to perceive these values and improving the efficiency of foreign trade activities of enterprises in the market under study.

Based on the results of systematizing the current trends in the development of the global watch market in modern conditions, and identifying the specific aspects and determinants of foreign trade activities of enterprises in the watch market, it is necessary to substantiate the strategic vectors of foreign trade activities of enterprises in the watch market in the context of geopolitical turbulence, which can be considered as tasks for further research.

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